

THE TEAM BEHIND

17 PARTNERS

10 COUNTRIES

UNIVERSIDAD
POLITÉCNICA
DE MADRID

satec_

STAY CONNECTED WITH US

earthone-project.eu

in X

info@earthone-project.eu

earthone

Environmental Analysis
and Resilience
for Transformative
Human-Optimised
Natural Environments

Funded by
the European Union

WHAT'S EARTHONE ABOUT

Our mission is to provide a comprehensive understanding of the **key drivers** that influence greenhouse gas (GHG) fluxes. Using this knowledge, we develop effective land management strategies to support communities in adapting to climate change.

KEY DRIVERS

SOCIO-ECONOMIC

Understanding how economic activities shape our environment.

DEMOGRAPHIC

Analysing population dynamics and their environmental impact.

PHYSICAL

Assessing natural and physical constraints influencing GHG emissions

WE HELP CREATE RESILIENT LANDSCAPES BY:

Implementing sustainable agriculture and forestry.

Using advanced **tech & AI** to monitor climate impact.

Equipping land managers and communities with vital **knowledge**.

Turning climate challenges into sustainable **growth** opportunities.

Researching how nature **adapts** to climate change.

OUR PILOTS LOCAL ACTION GLOBAL IMPACT

These **six pilots** across **six European countries** showcase diverse land use strategies tailored to local soil and climate conditions. Each site serves as a real-world case study testing innovative approaches to Improved Land Use Management to enhance sustainability, resilience, and environmental monitoring.

SPAIN

Land use: Agroforestry

Explores land succession from agriculture to dehesa ecosystems. Combines natural oak regeneration and biomass management via grazing. Includes automated field monitoring to assess soil health, carbon capture, and biodiversity.

ITALY

Land use: Agroforestry

Builds on long-term trials with poplar trees and crop rotation. Focuses on sustainable timber use, greenhouse gas mitigation, and soil carbon storage. Uses past and current data to model agroforestry benefits.

GREECE

Land use: Agriculture in cleared forest, agroforestry

Tests green fertilisation, manure use and local farming practices on apple orchards. Measures soil health, biodiversity, yields, and climate impact using smart sensors and microbiome analysis.

CROATIA

Land use: Wetlands

Assesses how extensive grazing affects wetland soil, water, and biodiversity. Studies invasive species and the wetlands' role in climate resilience and carbon retention.

SLOVENIA

Land use: Afforestation area (pasture to forest transition)

Examines soil changes and carbon storage as grasslands transition into forests. Enhances long-term monitoring of soil life, emissions, and vegetation cycles in karst and Mediterranean zones.

NORTH MACEDONIA

Land use: Intensive agriculture

Focuses on soil conservation, water retention, and erosion control in cherry orchards. Tests precision agriculture with digital tools like soil and crop health mapping for better fertiliser use.

